

NEAR-THRESHOLD PROPAGATION OF DELAMINATION FATIGUE CRACKS IN GRAPHITE/PEEK LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The influences of the stress ratio and water environment on the near-threshold growth of delamination fatigue cracks were investigated with unidirectional laminates made from APC-2 prepregs. Tests were carried out under mode I opening loading by using double cantilever beam specimens with a special loading device. The crack growth rate under different stress ratios was a unique function of the equivalent stress intensity range proposed by the authors. The fatigue crack growth rate near the threshold was mainly controlled by the stress range rather than the maximum stress. The fatigue crack growth resistance of APC-2 laminates was much higher than that of conventional graphite/epoxy laminates even near the threshold region. This increase of resistance, however, was smaller than that of fracture toughness. The tests in water at 23°C and 50°C showed no detrimental effects of environments. Lowering the frequency of stress cycling yielded accelerated crack growth, suggesting the time-dependent mechanism of crack growth.

INTRODUCTION

Composite structures used as primary structures require performance reliability based on damage tolerance. Conventional CFRP laminates made of brittle epoxy matrix have very low interlaminar strength, manifested as a low threshold of delamination fatigue crack growth and a low static fracture toughness^{1,2}. Hence, the improvement of delamination strength of CFRP laminates is of current interest in their structural applications.

Polyetheretherketone(PEEK) is a new semicrystalline thermoplastic matrix resin which is expected to improve significantly the interlaminar strength. The interlaminar fracture toughness of graphite/PEEK laminates was reported to be 3 to 4 times higher than that of conventional graphite/epoxy laminates (where the toughness is expressed in terms of the stress intensity factor)³. However, very little is known about the effect of cyclic loading on the delamination growth behavior in graphite/PEEK laminates. O'Brien⁴ suggested on the basis of the results of edge delamination tests that the delamination resistance of graphite/PEEK composite under fatigue loading was significantly lower than its delamination resistance under static loading.

In the present study, the influences of the stress ratio (the mean stress) and water environment on the near-threshold growth of delamination fatigue cracks were investigated. The results were compared with our previous results for graphite/epoxy laminates^{5,6}.

Table 1. Materials and elastic constants.

Pfepreg Carbon fiber Matrix	ICI APC-2 Hercules AS4 ICI PEEK
Volume fraction of fiber	62%
Constitution of laminate	(0) ₄₈
Crystallinity	38%
Elastic constants (GPa)	$E_1=134, E_2=8.9, G_{12}=5.1$ $\nu_{12}=0.37$
Fracture toughness K_{Ic} (MPam ^{1/2})	5.2

Fig. 1 DCB specimen with loading apparatus (dimensions are in mm).

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

1. Materials and specimen

The laminates were made from prepregs of ICI APC-2 (AS4/PEEK). The unidirectional laminates (thickness=6mm) were fabricated by ICI. The constitution of laminates, their elastic moduli, and their fracture toughness for mode I delamination are summarized in Table 1. The fracture toughness value was determined by using the same specimen as that used for fatigue testing.

Tests of delamination fatigue crack growth were carried out under mode I opening loading by using double cantilever beam specimens with a special loading device. Figure 1 shows the loading apparatus. Crack opening displacement on the load line was measured by an extensometer attached to the loading apparatus as shown in Fig. 1.

2. Fatigue tests

Tests were carried out with a computer-controlled fatigue testing system established by the authors^{2,5}. The fracture mechanics parameters were also calculated by the same procedure as before. In each test, the stress ratio, R , of the minimum to the maximum load was kept constant to be 0.2 or 0.5. A normalized gradient of energy release rate, $(1/G)dG/da$, was also controlled during load shedding. The relation between the crack growth rate and the energy release rate range was found to be identical in our previous study when the G -gradient was greater than -0.87 mm^{-1} . Tests were conducted at a G -gradient greater than this limit. The frequency of stress cycling was 10 Hz for the normal testing condition. Some tests were also carried out at 2 Hz to investigate the effect of frequency. The testing environment was air of 50%RH at 23°C, water at 23°C, and water at 50°C. The length of a crack was computed from the measurement of the compliance of the specimen².

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Effect of stress ratio on crack growth in air

Figure 2 shows the relation between the crack propagation rate, da/dN , and the stress intensity range, ΔK , under $R=0.2$ and 0.5, where $\Delta K = K_{\max} - K_{\min}$ (K_{\max} and K_{\min} are the maximum and minimum values of the stress intensity factor corresponding to the maximum and minimum loads). For each case of the stress ratio, da/dN is expressed as a power function of ΔK in the region where da/dN is larger than about 10^{-10} m/cycle . Below this region, da/dN deviates to the lower rate, and there exists a growth threshold for fatigue cracks. When compared with our previous study on graphite/epoxy⁵, the downward deviation in the da/dN vs. ΔK relation is not so clear near the threshold region. However, the slope is steep enough to suggest the existence of the growth threshold from a view point of engineering applications. The exponent of the power function and the R -dependency on da/dN are smaller than those for graphite/epoxy. Crack closure was not detected for the present tests.

For the case of graphite/epoxy laminates, the growth rate under different stress

Fig. 2 Relation between da/dN and ΔK in air.

Fig. 3 Relation between da/dN and ΔG in air.

ratios was fairly well correlated to ΔG . Thus, da/dN is plotted against ΔG in Fig. 3. The R -dependency is larger than that on the da/dN vs. ΔK relation. The effect of R on the da/dN vs. ΔG relation is also reversed in comparison with that on the da/dN vs. ΔK relation.

2. Controlling fracture mechanics parameter

In our previous analysis of the near-threshold crack growth⁵, we proposed the following equivalent stress intensity range, ΔK_{eq} as a controlling parameter for fatigue crack growth under various R values:

$$\Delta K_{eq} = \Delta K(1-R)^{-\gamma} = \Delta K^{(1-\gamma)} K_{max}^{\gamma} \quad (1)$$

where γ indicates a relative contribution of the maximum stress to the cyclic stress in determining the crack growth rate. ΔK_{eq} can be regarded as an equivalent parameter of ΔK at $R=0$ to which the R dependency of ΔK is converted.

In Fig. 4, ΔK at $da/dN=10^{-10}$ m/cycle is plotted against a stress ratio parameter, $(1-R)$, in order to obtain γ values. The results of the graphite/epoxy laminate (T300/914) are also shown with the triangle marks in this figure⁵. The exponent of a straight line fit of data gives the γ values. For the case of graphite/PEEK laminate, the γ values is 0.36 in air at 23°C and in water at 50°C, while it is 0.17 in water at 23°C. the detail of the data for water environment will be discussed later. These low values of γ suggest that the mechanism of fatigue crack propagation is mainly controlled by the stress intensity range (ΔK) like in metallic materials. On the other hand, the results of graphite/epoxy laminate fit to the line at the slope of 0.85. This slope means that the contribution of the maximum stress intensity factor (K_{max}) is larger than that of stress intensity range (ΔK)⁵. The influence of the stress ratio on the growth resistance is completely different between graphite/PEEK and graphite/epoxy. While ΔK of graphite/PEEK laminate is only 1.8 times that of graphite/epoxy laminate under

Fig. 4 Relation between ΔK and $(1-R)$ at $da/dN=10^{-10}$ m/cycle.

Fig. 5 Relation between da/dN and ΔK_{eq} in air.

$R=0$, the difference in ΔK is much larger at higher R values as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 5 shows the relation between da/dN and ΔK_{eq} . The influence of the stress ratio is minimal for the whole region. This means that ΔK_{eq} is the controlling fracture mechanics parameter for APC-2 laminate.

3. Comparison with graphite/epoxy

Figure 6 shows the relations between da/dN and ΔK_{eq} for APC-2 (graphite/PEEK) and 914C (graphite/epoxy) laminates. The resistance of the former material against fatigue crack growth is much higher than that of the latter material. When compared at the same growth rate, ΔK_{eq} value for APC-2 laminate is about twice as much as that for 914C laminate. When compared at the same ΔK_{eq} , da/dN for APC-2 laminates is about 4 orders of magnitude lower than that for 914C laminates. The exponent of the power function for APC-2 laminates reduced to three fourths.

Table 2 shows the values of $\Delta K_{eqth}/K_{IC}$ for graphite/epoxy (914C, P305) and graphite/PEEK (APC-2) where ΔK_{eqth} is the ΔK_{eq} value at the crack growth threshold. The value of $\Delta K_{eqth}/K_{IC}$ for APC-2 laminate is smaller than those for graphite epoxy laminates. Thus, the remarkable increase of fracture toughness, K_{IC} , for APC-2 laminates does not fully contribute to the increase of fatigue crack growth resistance near the threshold region. This fact indicates a larger contribution of fatigue in damage-tolerance design.

Fig. 6 Comparison between APC-2 and graphite/epoxy.

Table 2. Threshold conditions compared with fracture toughness.

Material	K_{IC} (MPam ^{1/2})	ΔK_{eqth} (MPam ^{1/2})	$\Delta K_{eqth}/K_{IC}$	γ
914C	1.4	0.75	0.54	0.86
P305	1.7	0.68	0.40	0.51
APC-2	5.2	1.2	0.23	0.36

Fig. 7 Relation between da/dN and ΔK_{eq} in water at 23°C.

4. Effect of water environment

Figure 7 shows the crack propagation rate in water at 23°C plotted against ΔK_{eq} , where $\gamma=0.17$ is used. There is a knee in the da/dN vs. ΔK_{eq} relation. da/dN is expressed as two power functions of ΔK_{eq} . The exponent of the power function is 11 in the region of rates larger than 5×10^{-10} m/cycle. Below this region, the exponent decreases to 7.1. No significant growth threshold is observed. In comparison with the results in air (dashed line), the rate decreased only by half in the high rate region. There is no significant effect of water environment near the threshold. Thus, the effect of water environment is much smaller than that for graphite/epoxy⁶. This fact may come from low moisture content for APC-2 laminate. The saturated content of moisture was 0.17% for APC-2 laminates and 2.5% for graphite/epoxy (914C) laminates.

Figure 8 shows the results in water at 50°C where $\gamma=0.36$. The knee is more significant in this case. When compared with the results in air at the same ΔK_{eq} , da/dN reduced to about half to one tenth. Since water environment enhanced the crack growth rate in graphite/epoxy laminate⁶, the environmental resistance of APC-2 laminate is much higher than that of graphite/epoxy laminates. The low value of the exponent of the power function in the low growth rate region and nonexistence of the growth threshold suggest the contribution of the time dependent mechanism to crack growth.

5. Effect of frequency of stress cycling

In order to find out the contribution of the time dependent mechanism, tests of delamination fatigue crack growth at a frequency of stress cycling of 2 Hz were carried out in air of 50%RH at 23°C, and in water at 23°C and at 50°C. The results are shown in Figs. 9, 10, and 11. In each figure, the results at 10 Hz are indicated

Fig. 9 Relation between da/dN and ΔK_{eq} in air at 23°C at 2Hz.

Fig. 10 Relation between da/dN and ΔK_{eq} in water at 23°C at 2Hz.

Fig. 8 Relation between da/dN and ΔK_{eq} in water at 50°C.

with the dashed lines. Since the tests were conducted only under $R=0.2$, γ values obtained at 10 Hz were used to compute ΔK_{eq} values. As shown in Fig. 9, there is no effect of the frequency on the growth behavior in air. On the other hand, increase of the growth rate and decrease of the exponent of the power function were observed in water. These differences were larger at higher temperature. For the case of the results in water at 50°C, the difference of the crack growth rate at the range of ΔK_{eq} of 1.5 to 2.0 MPam^{1/2} due to frequency difference was about five fold. Thus, the crack growth behavior in the low growth rate region is controlled by the time dependent mechanism instead of cyclic dependent mechanism. The change in the mechanism from cyclic-dependent one to time-dependent one gives the knee in the da/dN vs. ΔK_{eq} relation at 10 Hz as shown in Figs. 8 and 9.

CONCLUSIONS

A. The crack propagation rate under different stress ratios was expressed as a unique power function of the equivalent stress intensity range at the growth rates above about 10^{-10} m/cycle. Below this region, there was a growth threshold. The degree of contribution of the stress range was high. Graphite/PEEK laminates are more resistant to fatigue crack growth, showing a higher growth threshold, lower crack growth rates and a lower exponent in the power relation.

B. In comparison with the graphite/epoxy laminates, the ratio of the fracture toughness to the fatigue threshold increased. This fact indicates a larger contribution of fatigue consideration in damage-tolerance design.

C. The tests in water at 23°C and at 50°C showed no detrimental effect on crack growth. The threshold for fatigue crack growth was not observed. Lowering frequency of stress cycling yielded accelerated crack growth in the low rate region. The contribution of the time dependent mechanism was high.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank Dr. K. Kemmochi of Industrial Products Research Institute and K. Endo of LION Co. for their helpful discussion. This work is supported by the MITI program of R&D Project on Basic Technologies for Future Industries and Joint Government-Private Sector Research.

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Fig. 11 Relation between da/dN and ΔK_{eq} in water at 50°C at 2Hz.